

**ASSESSMENT OF AVAILABILITY AND
ADEQUACY OF INSTRUCTIONAL RESOURCES AND
TIME ALLOCATED FOR FURTHER MATHEMATICS INSTRUCTIONS
IN KOGI STATE, NIGERIA**

**Okpanachi, David¹,
Adeniyi, Gideon Sunday²ⁱ,
Umoru, Samuel Achem²**

¹PhD, Mathematics Department,
Kogi State College Of Education,
Ankpa, Nigeria

²Mathematics Department,
Kogi State College Of Education,
Ankpa, Nigeria

Abstract:

The paper highlights availability and adequate of instructional resources and time allocated for further mathematics instructions in Kogi State. The population for the study is 600 comprised of 100 further mathematics teachers and 500 further mathematics students from among which 52 teachers and 300 students were sampled. The instrument for data collection was questionnaire designed by the researchers. The instruments were validated by specialists in mathematics educations and measurement and evaluation. The reliability co-efficient of 0.81 and 0.91 were obtained for teachers and students respectively. The researchers generated three researched question and one hypothesis that was tested at a significance level of 0.05. Simple percentage, mean and standard deviation were used to analyzed the research questions and t-test to analyzed the hypothesis. The study found that most instructional resources were not available, the instructional resources were not adequate for further mathematics instructions and time allocated for further mathematics instructions were not adequate among others. The study also recommended that Government, Parent Teachers Associated (P.T.A) and other stakeholder as a matter of urgency provide relevant instructional resources for further mathematics instructions and times allocated for further mathematics should be increased from three (3) periods/week to daily to enable teachers/students to cover the course contents among others.

Keywords: availability and adequacy of instructional resources, instructional resources, mathematics instructions

ⁱ Correspondence: email adeniyigs@yahoo.com

1. Introduction

The teacher is the most important in the determination of what takes place in any classroom. According to Ekpo (2004), the teacher's total performance in a classroom is a function of his training experience which includes effective use of instructional resources (also called instructional materials). No matter how good and well planned curricula may be lack of adequate knowledge of the subject matter as well as lack/inadequate instructional resources to work with can militate against its successful implementation.

Mathematics is one of the most powerful and acceptable tools which the intelligence of man has made for its own use over the centuries (Usman, 2002). Beside, mathematics is an important subject that is indispensable to the technological development of any nation. According to Okpanachi (2016), mathematics gave birth to additional mathematics and later to Further Mathematics (F.M). The major critics of modern mathematics/general mathematics was that the curricula for SSS level did not cater for the brighter students who would wish either to study mathematics, engineer mechanic sciences or other related science subject in the university and other tertiary institution. As a result of the above criticism further mathematics curricula was approved in 1985 and institutionalized in Nigeria Senior Secondary School (SSS).

Further Mathematics, curricula is aimed at bridging the inadequacies of additional mathematics and it provides the opportunity for brighter students who may wish to study science related course at tertiary levels. Also, National Examination Council of Nigeria (NECO, 2015), noted that further mathematics syllabus was developed to meet the need of potential students of Mathematics related profession like Engineering, Physics and Mathematics.

Neco (2015) also noted that there were indication of none coverage of FM course contents. In order to produce future scientist, Engineers, medical doctors, pharmacist and technician to great number and quality, a sound knowledge of further mathematics at Senior Secondary School level is required. According to Okpanachi (2016), further mathematics is an important subject that is indispensable to the technological development of any nation. Despite the perceived importance of further mathematics in science and technology, certain factors have been identified as being responsible for the problem of teaching and learning of further mathematics. Some of the problems identified by Ibrahim (2004) include not adhering to the policy guide by further mathematics teachers and non-use of instructional resources. In attempt to solve some of these problems mathematics educators and mathematicians initiated a comprehensive programme towards the effectives teaching/learning of further mathematics at SSS level. One of the strategies was the introduction and use of instructional resource in teaching/learning.

Instructional resources are the resources or teaching materials that the teachers use in presenting the lesson so that the students can easily understand what is being taught. Instructional resources according to Offorma cited in Okpanachi (2016) are all

about ways or means of making teaching and learning process more meaningful, effective, productive and understandable.

In addition, Abdu-Raheen (2016) submitted that instructional materials are essential and significant tools needed for teaching and learning of school subjects to promote teacher's efficiency and improve student's performance. They made learning more interesting, practical, realistic and appealing. They also enable both teachers and students to participate actively and effecting in lesson sessions. They give room for acquisition of skills, knowledge and development of self-confidence and self-actualization.

In addition, Ajayi and Ayodele cited in Abdu-Raheen (2016) stressed the importance of availability and adequacy of instructional resources/materials to achieving effectiveness in educational delivery and supervision in school system. Ogbondah (2008), alerted on gross inadequacy and underutilization of instructional materials necessary to compensate for the inadequacies of sense organs and to reinforce the capacity of dominant organs.

However, Akinleye (2010) attested that effective teaching and learning requires a teacher to teach the students with instructional resources and use practical activities to make learning more vivid, logical, and realistic and pragmatic. From the above contributions, instructional resources are all things that are used to support, facilitate, influence or encourage acquisition of knowledge, competency and skills.

According to Okpanachi (2016), the blue print for effective implement of further mathematics curricula includes; well-furnished classroom, staffroom, well equipped mathematics laboratories, large quantities of instructional resources among other.

Instructional resources includes charts of various type, geo board, computer set, chalkboard, compasses, protractors, abacus, magnetic board, video tape etc. these material should be assess periodically for effectives utilization. Okpanachi (2016) also asserted that most instructional materials are not available in schools.

Assessment which means the procedure and processes employed in collecting information. Asiru (2015) asserted that assessment is a process in which one makes a judgment about a person or situation.

Time allocation is the period set aside for the teaching and learning of subject activities. The time allocated for further mathematics instructions is three times in a week (Okpanachi, 2016). The researchers want to find out if these periods are enough for further mathematics instructions in Kogi state. According to Asiru (2015), who observed that time allocation in teaching and learning of mathematics is adequate.

1.1 Statement of the problem

The observed annual low level performance of further mathematics students in both local and external examination evolved the concern of stakeholders in education industry including the researchers. Could the low performance of further mathematics students be as results of inadequate instructional resources? This study therefore deems it necessary to assess the adequacy of instructional resources and times allocation for effective implementation of further mathematics curricula.

1.2 Purpose of the study

The main purpose of this study is the assessment of adequacy of instructional resources and time allocated for the implementation of further mathematics instructions.

Specifically, the study intended to find out;

1. Availability of instructional resources for further mathematics instructions.
2. Adequacy of instructional resources for further mathematics instructions
3. The mean rating of teachers and students on the adequacy of numbers of times allocated for further mathematics instructions on the timetable.

1.3 Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study;

1. Are instructional resources available for effective teaching and learning of further mathematics?
2. Are the available instructional resources adequate for further mathematics instructions?
3. What are the mean ratings of teachers and students on the adequacy of number of times/periods allocated for further mathematics instructions on the timetable?

1.4 Hypothesis

The following hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance guided the study.

H₀: There is no significant difference between the mean rating of teachers and students on the adequacy of numbers of time allocated for further mathematics instructions on the timetable.

2. Methodology

The type of design used in this paper is a survey research design. It was adopted because of its relevance to the study. This method makes use of the questionnaire which is economical in nature and gives access to a large population of students and teachers at the same times.

2.1 Population of the study

The population of this study is 600 persons comprising of 500 and 100 further mathematics teachers and students respectively.

2.2 Sample and sampling techniques

Simple random sampling techniques was used to select 300 and 52 further mathematics students and teachers respectively from the three (3) senatorial zones of the state. The sample size comprising of 120 and 20 further mathematics students and teachers respectively from Kogi east senatorial zones, 100 and 18 further mathematics students and teacher respectively from Kogi west senatorial zones 80 and 14 further mathematics students and teachers from Kogi central senatorial zones.

2.3 Research instrument

The instrument used in this research was the questionnaire developed by the researchers. The instruments were two, one for further mathematics teacher and the other for F.M students.

There are three (3) sections in the questionnaire, sections A has items on the availability of instructional resources, section B has items on the adequacy of instructional resources and section C has items on adequacy of time allocation for further mathematics instruction. The questionnaires consist of 30 items.

2.4 Validation of research instruments

Face validity was ensured by giving the questionnaire to two (2) experts in mathematics education and one (1) expert in measurement and evaluation in the department of science education, University of Nigeria Nsuka.

2.5 Reliability of the research instrument

The reliability of the instrument was carried out by subjecting the instrument to three (3) schools which were not among the sampled schools. The reliability coefficient for teachers and students were 0.81 and 0.79 respectively

2.6 Method of data analysis

Simple percentage was used to analyzed research question 1 and 2. Standard deviation and mean was used for research question 3. t-test was used to test hypothesis 1. 50% and above was regarded as available while below 50% is not available. A mean value of 2.50 and above implies agreed while mean value below 2.50 was regarded as disagreed.

3. Results

Research Questions 1: Are instructional resources available for effective teaching and learning of further mathematics?

Table 1: Teachers' responses on availability of instructional resources

Instructional Resources	Yes		No	
	F	%	F	%
Textbook	21	40	31	60
Chart	28	54	24	46
Geo board	5	10	30	90
Computer	5	10	47	90
Calculators	36	69	16	31
Compasses	24	46	28	54
Protractors	20	39	32	61
Rulers	28	54	24	46
Chalkboard	33	64	19	36
Abacus	5	10	49	90
Globes	5	10	47	90
Cardboard paper	20	39	32	61

Okpanachi, David, Adeniyi, Gideon Sunday, Umoru, Samuel Achem
 ASSESSMENT OF AVAILABILITY AND ADEQUACY OF INSTRUCTIONAL RESOURCES AND
 TIME ALLOCATED FOR FURTHER MATHEMATICS INSTRUCTIONS IN KOGI STATE, NIGERIA

Plain shapes	12	23	40	77
Solid shape	22	42	30	58
Magnetic Boards	15	29	37	71
Graph sheets	20	39	32	61
Drawing sheets	23	44	29	56
Cords	10	19	42	81
Puzzle boxes	12	23	40	77
Mathematics kit	12	23	40	77

Table 1 indicates that most available instructional resources were chart, calculators, rulers and chalkboards. According to the findings textbooks, compasses, solid shapes and drawing sheets were fairly available. Most of the respondents indicates that geo boards, computer, protractor, abacus, globes, cardboard paper, plain shapes, magnetic board, cards, puzzle box and mathematics kits were not available.

Research Question 2: Are the instructional resources that are available adequate for further mathematics instructions?

Table 2: Teachers responses on the level of adequacy of instrument resources (n=52)

Responses	Frequency	%
Adequate	8	15
Slightly adequate	10	19
Inadequate	32	62
None	2	4
Total	52	100

Instructional resources are important in teaching further mathematics as they help the students with dyscalculia to remember formulas, instructions and rules. Table 2 shows that only 15% of the instructional resources are adequate for further mathematics instruments, 19% of instructional materials were slightly adequate and 62% of instructional materials are inadequate.

Research Question 3: What are the mean rating of teachers and students on the adequacy of the member of times allocated on the table for further mathematics instructions?

Table 3: Means rating of teachers and students responses on the adequacy of time allocation for further mathematics instructions

Items Students	Teachers N=52			Students N=300		
	$\bar{X}_1$	SD ₁	DEC ₁	$\bar{X}_2$	SD ₂	DEC ₂
Further mathematics is taught once in a week.	1.6	0.9	D	1.92	0.97	D
Further mathematics is taught twice in a week	2.42	1.02	D	2.36	0.88	D
Further mathematics is taught three times in a week	2.79	1.30	A	2.60	1.11	A
Further mathematics is taught four time in a week	1.80	0.70	D	2.10	0.67	D
Further mathematics is taught daily	1.4	0.56	D	2.1	0.87	D

Key: N = number of respondents, $\bar{X}_1$ = mean for teacher, SD1, standard deviation for teachers, Dec1 = decision for teacher; $\bar{X}_2$ = means for students, SD2 = standard deviation for students; Dec2 = Decision for students.

Table 3 shows the means responses and standard deviation of the adequacy of number of times allocated for further mathematics instructions on the time table to cover the course content. Both teachers and students had mean less than 2.50 for items 1,2,4,5 and 6. Also, both teachers and students had a mean greater than 2.5 for item 3. Teachers and students agreed that further mathematics is taught three times/ week in most schools.

Hypothesis: There is no significant difference between the mean rating of teachers and students on the adequacy of number of time allocated for further mathematics instructions on the timetable.

Table 4: t-test analysis of significance difference of the means ratings of teachers and students responses on the adequacy of number of times allocated for further mathematics instruction on the timetable to cover the course contents

Items Students	Teachers N=52			Students N=300					
	$\bar{X}$	SD	$\bar{X}$	SD	T-cal	dt	sig	DEC	
Further mathematics is taught once/week	1.67	0.90	1.92	0.97	-1.79	350	0.07	NS	
Further mathematics is taught twice/week	2.42	1.02	2.75	0.88	-2.54	350	0.01	S	
Further Mathematics is taught three time/week	2.79	1.30	2.60	1.11	-1.19	350	0.24	NS	
Further mathematics thought four time/week	1.66	0.89	1.30	1.00	-1.80	350	0.06	NS	
Further mathematics is taught daily	1.88	0.68	1.95	0.83	-0.59	350	0.56	NS	
Cluster	2.19	0.47	2.13	0.50	-0.59	350	0.11	NS	

Table 4 showed that items 1,3,4 and 5 had t-value of 0.07, 0.24, 0.06 and 0.56 respectively. Since the associated probabilities for item 1,3,4 and 5 were greater than 0.05 level of significance, it means that there is no significant difference, this shows that there was significant different between the teachers and students responses. However, the cluster which is 0.11 is greater than 0.05 level of significant, this implies that the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference between means rating of teachers and students responses on the adequacy of time allocated to cover the course contents was rejected.

4. Discussion

The results revealed that most of the schools do not have some of the basic instructional resources for further mathematics instructions. This agreed with Okpanachi (2016), who stated that most instructional materials are not available in Senior Secondary Schools for further mathematics instructions. The only available instructional resources are charts, calculators and chalkboard.

This study also confirmed that most instructional resources available are inadequate for the implementation of the further mathematics curricula in Senior

Secondary Schools. This finding is in time with, Ogbondah (2008), Abdu-Raheem (2016) and Okpanachi (2016) who observed that most instructional resources/materials are inadequate for mathematics/further mathematics instruction in schools.

This study also revealed that time allocated for further mathematics instructions on the timetable is grossly inadequate. Further mathematics required more than three periods/ week which is what is being practiced in most schools in Kogi State. Teachers and students accepted that most further mathematics course contents were never covered. This finding in line with Okpanachi (2016) and Neco (2015) who asserted that further mathematics contents are not always covered as a result of limited time allocated. However, this finding is in construct with Asiru (2015) who stated that the time allocated for mathematics instructions are adequate.

The study showed that there is no statistical significant difference between the mean rating of teachers and students on the adequacy of the members of times allocated to further mathematics instruction on the time table to cover the course content.

5. Conclusion

The study concluded that lack or inadequate instructional resources in Secondary Schools can surely lead to poor acquisition of the knowledge of further mathematics students and poor performance in senior secondary certificate examinations and other related sciences. Hence, the importance of instructional resources in the development of learners' intellectual abilities and attainment of teaching/learning objectives cannot be over-emphasized. Further mathematics teachers should improvised (were not available) and use instructional resources in the classroom.

5.1 Recommendation

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were therefore made:

1. Efforts should be made Government, school authorities and professional bodies to equipped schools with necessary instructional resources for effective implementation of further mathematics curricular in senior secondary schools.
2. Government and Parent Teachers Association (PTA) should supply teaching materials and finance schools to enable improvised unavailable and inadequate instructional resources to make teaching and learning easier, practical, enjoyable and appealing.
3. Teachers should always try their best to make use of available instructional resources where necessary to make their lesson more interesting.
4. Time allocated on the timetable should be increased from three (3) periods/week to five (5) periods/week (daily). This will enable further mathematics teachers and students to cover further mathematics course contents.

References

1. Abdu-Raheem, B.O (2016). Effects of instructional materials on secondary schools' Academic Achievement in society studies in Ekiti State, Nigeria. *World Journal of Education*, 6(1), 32-39.
2. Akinleye, G.A (2010). Enhancing the quality of life in this complicated but dynamic world. 25th inquired Lecture, University of Ado-Ekiti, April 6.
3. Asiru, T.M (2015). Assessment of time allocation in teaching and learning of mathematics. Proceeding of 52nd and National Conference of Mathematical Association of Nigeria (MAN). Ilorin; Olad Publishers.
4. Ekpo, O.E (2004). Instructional strategies and the challenges of implementing of school curricula in Nigeria. Lead paper presented at 17th Annual Conference of Curricula Organization of Nigeria CON held at University of Uyo, Akwa Ibom State 14th - 17th September.
5. Ibrahim, G. (2004). The state of Further Mathematics curricula in Secondary Schools of Sokoto state. *Journal of Mathematics Association of Nigeria (Abacus)*, 29(1), 24 – 28.
6. Necon, (2014) Chief examiners report on June/July schools certificate examination. Minna: NERD. Press.
7. Ogbonda, L (2008). An appraised of instructional materials used to education migrant fisherman children in River State, Nigeria. *Interactional Journal of Scientific Rachael in Education*, 1 (1), 13-25.
8. Okpanachi, D. (2016). Evaluation of implementation of further mathematics curricula in senior secondary schools in Kogi State, Nigeria. Unpublished Ph.D Thesis, Department of science Education, University of Nigeria, Nsukka.
9. Usman, K.O (2002). The need to re-train in service mathematics teachers for the attainment of the objectives, of the universal basics education (UBE). *A journal of Mathematics Association of Nigeria (Abacus)* 27(1), 37-44.

Creative Commons licensing terms

Author(s) will retain the copyright of their published articles agreeing that a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) terms will be applied to their work. Under the terms of this license, no permission is required from the author(s) or publisher for members of the community to copy, distribute, transmit or adapt the article content, providing a proper, prominent and unambiguous attribution to the authors in a manner that makes clear that the materials are being reused under permission of a Creative Commons License. Views, opinions and conclusions expressed in this research article are views, opinions and conclusions of the author(s). Open Access Publishing Group and European Journal of Education Studies shall not be responsible or answerable for any loss, damage or liability caused in relation to/arising out of conflicts of interest, copyright violations and inappropriate or inaccurate use of any kind content related or integrated into the research work. All the published works are meeting the Open Access Publishing requirements and can be freely accessed, shared, modified, distributed and used in educational, commercial and non-commercial purposes under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License \(CC BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).